

Furniture Swapping For Youth Empowerment Through TVET And Circular Economy In Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates furniture swapping as a novel way to youth empowerment through Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria, using Jaebee Furniture as a case study. In light of rising youth unemployment and increasing environmental challenges, the study investigates how the principles of Zero Waste (ZW) and Circular Economy (CE) might be integrated into vocational skills training. Jaebee Furniture, a local firm that specializes in sustainable furniture design and reuse, acts as a model for displaying how unwanted or unused furniture may be converted into valuable items while providing young people with job skills. The study uses in-depth interviews to demonstrate the potential of furniture swapping to encourage skill learning, entrepreneurship, and environmental sustainability. The findings imply that incorporating furniture swapping into TVET curricula might minimize waste, promote green innovation, and generate long-term income-generating opportunities for Nigerian adolescents. The report closes by suggesting legislative support, institutional collaborations, and scalable frameworks for integrating furniture swapping as a viable instrument for youth empowerment and circular economy development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Furniture Swapping, TVET, Youth Empowerment, and Zero Waste

INTRODUCTION

With the growing digital realm exhibiting notable changes in many industries, the dynamic range of technical innovation has been demonstrated globally in recent years. It makes sense to refocus Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) on business and youth empowerment in light of the current circumstances facing Africa and Nigeria at large. This is because it will assist in tackling the issues of unemployment, poverty, and instability among many youths in the nation [12]. Africa, a continent that is frequently disregarded in the digital revolution, is actively making waves. More precisely, the diaspora-led technology growth and digital transformation in the furniture and textile industry has been crucial to the region's sustainable development [7]. The acronym TVET represents Technical and Vocational Education and Training. It emphasizes giving pupils the information and abilities they need to succeed in a particular trade or career. [17] in a similar vein, proposed that TVET can boost employability, productivity, creativity, and entrepreneurship, among other advantages for people, society, and the economy. For Africa, Nigeria's economic growth and the welfare of its youth, technical and vocational education and training (TVET) must be reoriented towards youth empowerment and entrepreneurship. According to the World Youth Report, there are about 1.2 billion young people in the 15–24 age group who face various development-related difficulties globally

(International Labor Organization [ILO] (2020), (United Nations [UN] (2020), outlined the primary obstacles to youth development as limited economic opportunities, a lack of labor market-ready skills, and a congested educational system that does not sufficiently prepare young people for work [2]. The value of TVET in reducing youth unemployment and promoting economic growth is becoming increasingly acknowledged in Africa, Nigeria, and many other nations. By reorienting TVET, educators and politicians hope to foster an atmosphere that encourages youth to become innovators, job creators, and contributors to the nation's economy.

Thus, among other things, this paper talks about how to improve youth employability and entrepreneurial skills in TVET through the use of furniture swapping in skill development, entrepreneurship practice encouragement, apprenticeship, and internship practice, among others. A considerable percentage of the world's furniture woods are agronomics in Africa, making the furniture sector a dynamic part of the continent's economy [19]. For furniture companies, the circular economy provides a paradigm whereby goods are manufactured from materials that may be recycled or replaced as they reach the end of their useful lives. In a circular economy, the business can strengthen its relationship with customers by using reverse logistics, which involves returning products for recycling or remanufacturing while also saving money and resources for the environment and the

entire economy [14]. By offering skill development, encouraging creativity, and promoting sustainability, furniture swapping programs can empower young people and may even result in job prospects and community involvement. According to O'Connell (Time for the Youth to Engage with the National Development Plan, 2019.), Young people in certain communities are also subjected to economic stagnation, gender inequity, and violence; these issues act as a deterrent to young people into the workforce [11]. Seventy-four million (74.8 million) young people globally are unemployed, growing from 11.8% in 2018 to 12.7% in 2019, according to a 2019 International Labor Organization (ILO, 2020b) report. Many Africans and Nigerians seemed hopeless and had lost faith in their nation. In 2023, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in Nigeria

Fig 1(SUN SKIPS, 2023)

reported that unemployment rates soared to 4.1% in the first quarter.

Home and office furnishings and appliances that are essential for everyone's daily life have now become difficult to purchase. Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) can be used to accomplish this. This kind of schooling tends to empower young people by giving them chances to start their businesses. But furniture swap is not given much thought when it comes to disposal and reuse. Usually, used furniture is sorted with other municipal trash and dumped in landfills, where it will ultimately break down Fig. 1. This method gravely harms the environment and is not cost-effective. Most furniture, including chairs and desks, is fairly durable and long-lasting Fig. 2.

Fig 2 (Furniture Link, 2020)

The furniture sector is under growing pressure to move into a circular economy (CE), notwithstanding its economic importance. There is a growing awareness of the need for circular practices that support resource efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable development because the conventional linear model of "take-make-dispose" is no longer viable [19]. As an alternate remedy, the CE suggests a closed-loop system for material flow, providing a theoretical framework, resources, and techniques for incorporating sustainability into society and business to lessen impacts on the environment and enhance the land. Nevertheless, the furniture manufacturing sector has gradually embraced CE standards, especially those about reuse, which should still take precedence over landfill, incineration, and recycling [3]. CE has garnered a lot of interest from scholars, professionals, and governments throughout the last ten years. Particularly at the polytechnic level, TVET programs should put more of an emphasis on fostering the technical know-how, practical skills, and competencies that employers demand. This means that these essential components of TVET must be included in Africa's and Nigeria's tertiary education curriculum.

Swapping furniture is an inexpensive, effective tactic that promotes environmental sustainability and youth empowerment. By empowering youth to be change agents in the circular economy, we cultivate a generation that has the mentality and abilities needed for a future with zero waste. Furniture swapping has the potential to grow as a youth development pathway and a climate solution through education, collaboration, and creativity. A zero-waste (ZW) system involves producing, using, recycling, and disposing of materials, products, and packaging in an acceptable manner—all without burning them or releasing any pollutants into the air, water, or land that might be harmful to the environment or public health [23]. Furniture swaps are necessary when choosing a career for a healthy life. These have the power to persuade young men and women to pursue productive jobs and avoid political thuggery, which is mostly supported by the political elite for their gain, truancy, and waywardness. Competencies and skills are becoming increasingly crucial in the fields of CE and ZW where vibrant youth can be productive. The amount of rubbish on the globe is going to erode society unless something systematic is done. ZW mechanisms will probably be employed to reduce waste and empower the youth, but CE mechanisms will be utilized by enterprises and industries to

promote resource efficiency and eliminate waste when items are made with the idea of being recycled and repurposed [9]. This implies that these essential components of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) must also be included in Africa's postsecondary education curriculum. The Furniture Swap was an exchange initiative, in which customers exchanged their old furniture for new one Fig. 3,4.

Since the use of furniture affects how a home and offices are perceived to be, reusing it in a local circular economy will help advance social, economic, and environmental sustainability by avoiding the negative environmental effects of product reuse and providing greater economic access to those with limited resources [4], [10].

Fig 3 (tes, 2024)

Fig 4 (Margolles & John, 1993)

Fig 5(Norwich Uni of Arts, 2021)

Youths must be given the required business and entrepreneurial skills to cultivate an entrepreneurial attitude, which will ultimately lead to their success as entrepreneurs. The majority of furniture is discarded because it breaks or becomes damaged (obsolescence of function), but a large portion of it is also discarded when it becomes unattractive or goes out of style [16] Fig 5. As a result, those involved in education, TVET specifically, will have to supply sufficient labs and workshops, the tools needed for efficient skill development. Changing an entire office suite is more common than changing individual components. The old furniture will be assessed to give a credit value, which will be used to partly offset the cost of the new furniture. The returned furniture will then be refurbished and sold to another customer who could equally return the same furniture after use, under the furniture swap arrangement. These swap concepts can be addressed and critically reflected in sustainability education, even if rarely taught. It will also provide apprenticeship and internship opportunities for the youth. Apprenticeships that provide hands-on experience can help TVET students develop their abilities and foster entrepreneurship. Youths can further hone their abilities and obtain real-world experience through this practical exposure. Fixtures are therefore found, improved, made, and sold to clients as furniture parts that, after being used, they simply exchanged for newer models. Due to its short lifespan and lack of biodegradability, furniture ends up filling landfills. When addressing the issue of zero-waste furniture, the concepts of sharing and circular economies are relevant. The conventional "throw-away attitude" of consumers, which involves first consuming and then disposing, is linked both economically and linearly. Peer-to-peer sharing of access to commodities or services through ownership transfer, including the purchase of used goods, is included in the sharing economy.

Youth empowerment is critical to the peace, security, and general growth of any nation. Rapid furniture disposal brought on by the advent of consumerism has greatly increased landfill trash and resource depletion. At the same time, young people everywhere are calling for more inclusive roles in the fight against climate change. This study suggests furniture swapping as a two-pronged intervention that encourages zero-waste behaviors within the context of the circular economy while giving young people agency and useful skills. One of the fastest-growing furniture manufacturers in Nigeria, JAEBEE FURNITURE, has collaborated with us on this study. This cooperative endeavor ensured that wood for furniture was cut to precise sizes, thereby reducing wastage. The production of all off-cuts allowed for their potential repurposing as smaller components of furniture. For smaller decorative elements, wood offcuts were also utilized. Throw pillows and other soft furnishings, including foam kids' toys, were made from old cushions and foam that customers returned. Ornamental pieces were also made from the fabrics of the antique furniture. The low-income earners, mostly youths, students, and job seekers, constituted a new market group made available by this effort. The primary aim of this paper is to investigate the integration of furniture swapping into Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a pragmatic instrument for youth empowerment in Nigeria, while fostering zero-waste habits and supporting a circular economy. This will result in a greater focus being placed on producing skilled individuals for the academic and furniture industries.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Nigeria confronts ongoing issues of youth unemployment, waste management, and restricted access to practical skills training, notwithstanding the increasing demand for sustainable development solutions. Technical and Vocational Education and

Training (TVET) is acknowledged as a means to provide youth with employable skills; nevertheless, numerous TVET programs are often underutilized, antiquated, or misaligned with new, ecologically friendly methods. At the same time, Nigeria faces significant levels of waste generation and low adoption of circular economy concepts, particularly in the furniture industry, where large amounts of used or discarded materials go unmanaged. While furniture swapping offers the chance to reuse and upcycle resources, lengthen product lifecycles, and reduce waste, its promise as a practical, skills-based strategy in TVET is virtually untapped. The problem is that the relationship between furniture swapping, TVET, and youth empowerment within a zero-waste and circular economy framework has not been thoroughly researched or institutionalized in Nigeria. Without such integration, Nigerian young continue to miss out on chances for entrepreneurship, skill development, and sustainable livelihoods, while the country lags in adopting circular economy norms.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To investigate the integration of furniture swapping into Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a pragmatic instrument for youth empowerment in Nigeria, while fostering zero-waste habits and supporting a circular economy. The objectives are:

1. To investigate the use of furniture swapping as an innovative technique for skill learning among Nigerian adolescents in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)
2. To analyze how furniture swapping can encourage zero-waste behaviors and contribute to Nigeria's circular economy
3. To assess the ability of furniture swapping efforts to generate job and business opportunities for adolescents and young adults
4. To explore difficulties and enablers in incorporating furniture swapping into TVET programs for long-term youth empowerment
5. To offer a framework for implementing furniture swapping as a scalable model of TVET for promoting sustainability and youth development in Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How may furniture swapping be incorporated into Technical and Vocational Education and

Training (TVET) to boost youth empowerment in Nigeria?

2. How can furniture exchanging encourage zero-waste behaviors and contribute to the circular economy?
3. What chances does furniture exchanging provide for Nigerian youngsters to learn skills, find work, and start their own businesses?
4. What are the problems and constraints to adopting furniture swapping in Nigerian TVET programs?
5. What framework or model can be created to make furniture swapping a sustainable TVET practice that promotes youth empowerment and circular economy growth?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Jaebee furniture industry in Lagos, Nigeria. The company was chosen because of its establishment in innovative furniture solutions, aiming at cost reduction, an increase in efficiency, and service quality for the privileged and underprivileged people of Lagos State and Nigeria. This study investigates how the Nigerian commercial furniture sector exemplifies a "circular and zero waste economy," or how material resources are preserved for as long as feasible to maximize, recover, or exploit their value. The research method for this study is based on a qualitative study using unstructured (in-depth) interviews as tools to extract useful information for the paper. The interview was later transcribed to elucidate the procedures on how the events of swapping furniture typify. This method works well for understanding modern practices and phenomena as well as providing background information on real problems that are yet unclear. The analysis was used in this study primarily to describe the degree to which businesses in the furniture industry are implementing sustainability and circular economy strategies. Community organizations in Nigeria sometimes gather furniture pieces, fix them if needed, and then sell or donate them to help underprivileged households or the furniture industry. This exercise benefited from this largesse under the furniture swap arrangement. About 40% of the old furniture collected from customers that its members gathered for recycling, repair, and reuse was used again for newer furniture, while the remaining percentage was used for smaller soft furnishings such as cushions, throw pillows

Fig 8: Used Furniture

Fig 9: Dilapidated Furniture

Fig 10: Refurbished Furniture

To ensure the life cycle environmental performance of the furniture that is sold to the customer, the company specifically provides furniture along with additional comprehensive services, such as design, maintenance, repair, upgrading, substitution, reconfiguration, and furniture end-of-life treatment

DISCUSSION

Zero Waste (ZW) and Circular Economy (CE)

The principles of Zero Waste (ZW) and Circular Economy (CE) have gained international prominence as sustainable strategies for resource management, focusing on waste reduction and the prolongation of product lifespans. One of the main objectives behind the formation of the Zero Waste International

Alliance in 2002 was to set guidelines for the global implementation of Zero Waste [23]. The goal of zero waste is to help the youth change their habits and lifestyles to mimic sustainable natural cycles, in which all materials that are wasted are intended to become resources for future use. Zero Waste prioritizes the reduction, reuse, and recycling of materials to eradicate reliance on landfills, whereas Circular Economy advocates for the perpetual circulation of resources via repair, refurbishing, and upcycling. Both notions are significantly pertinent in Nigeria, where elevated young unemployment levels coincide with urgent issues of waste generation and inadequate environmental policies.

Fig 6: Zero Waste Hierarchy (ZWIA, 2022) Fig 7: Circular Economy Process (Arowana, 2023)

An alternative to the conventional line of economy is the circular economy (make, use, dispose) [6]. The "circular economy" is a paradigm for production and consumption that emphasizes renting, sharing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing, and recycling existing resources and products for as long as practical. In this approach, the goods' life cycle is extended. In this context, furniture swapping exemplifies the practical implementation of zero waste and circular economy concepts by promoting the reuse and repurposing of existing furniture instead of disposal. These have the potential to be productively utilized repeatedly, adding even more value [5]. Many organizations view the circular economy as a potential solution to global challenges. Integrating these methods into Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) enables Nigerian teenagers to develop practical skills in

upcycling, design innovation, and sustainable production. This not only solves environmental concerns, but also creates opportunities for entrepreneurship, job development, and revenue generating, reducing youth unemployment. Furthermore, furniture swapping coincides with CE by encouraging a culture of value retention—materials that would otherwise be discarded are converted into marketable products. TVET may train young people to transform abandoned furniture into aesthetically pleasing and practical things, hence creating chances for green businesses and local firms. This method also improves Nigeria's push for sustainable development by combining skills training, waste reduction, and economic empowerment.

The procedure of furniture swap is in five (5) Steps. Fig 11:

CONCLUSION

Furniture swapping is a low-cost, high-impact strategy that blends adolescent empowerment with environmental sustainability. We can produce a generation that has the mindset and abilities required for a zero-waste future by enabling young people to be changemakers in the circular economy. Through cooperation, education, and ingenuity, furniture swapping can develop into a means of fostering youth development and addressing climate change. This study elucidates circular design strategies in the furniture business with a view toward the future. These revelations could motivate scholars and professionals to create programs, agreements, plans, and materials that support execution in this area. This exploratory study is to offer insightful information that might be reinforced and bolstered by further data in order to promote the sustainable transition in the furniture sector. In conclusion, incorporating Zero Waste and Circular Economy ideas into TVET through furniture swapping not only equips Nigerian students with practical skills, but also encourages a shift in mindset toward sustainability and innovation. This places young people as active drivers of environmental stewardship and economic growth in the country.

REFERENCE

1. Arowana. (2023, January 19). The Circular Economy - Everything You Need to Know | Arowana Impact Capital | Arowana. Arowana Impact Capital, Insight. <https://arowanaco.com/2023/01/19/circular-economy-everything-you-need-to-know/>
2. Arutyunova, A. E., Khanseviarov, R. I., Okunkova, E. A., Alieva, P. R., & Makareva, E. A. (2022). Youth, Work and Skills: A Map of the Transformation of the Workforce and Employment. *Studies in Big Data*, 110, 149–160. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04903-3_18
3. Barbaritano, M., Bravi, L., & Savelli, E. (2019). Sustainability and Quality Management in the Italian Luxury Furniture Sector: A Circular Economy Perspective. *Sustainability* 2019, Vol. 11, Page 3089, 11(11), 3089. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU11113089>
4. Castellani, V., Sala, S., & Mirabella, N. (2015). Beyond the throwaway society: A life cycle-based assessment of the environmental benefit of reuse. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 11(3), 373–382. <https://doi.org/10.1002/IEAM.1614>
5. European Parliament. (2023, May 24). Circular economy: definition, importance and benefits | Topics | European Parliament. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20151201STO05603/circular-economy-definition-importance-and-benefits>
6. Fekry Gamal, D. (2022). Concept of Circular Economy in Eco-Friendly Furniture Design Introduction. 1. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jdsaa.2021.101152.1140>
7. Franc Ter, A., & Brigid, O. I. (2024). Diaspora-led Technological Innovations and Digital Transformation in Africa: Investigating the Contributions to Technological Advancements and Digital Transformation in Finance and Telecommunications for Sustainable Development. *West African Journal on Sustainable Development*, 1(2), 121–132. <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/wajsd/article/view/3925>
8. Furniture Link. (2020). Furniture is societies least-recycled household item! - Furniture Link Inc. <https://www.furniturelink.co/public/609-2/>
9. Glavič, P., Szilagyi, A., Karouti, I., Kostoulas, A., Hernaez, O., Atín, E., Rocha, C. S., Camocho, D., Žiberna, B., Karadimas, D., Ruzicka, P., Schönfelder, T., Karouti, I., Stawecka, G., Hammerl, B., Schnitzer, H., & Dolinsky, M. (2019). Education for Zero Waste and the Circular Economy Sector in Europe Zero Waste and Circular Economy Sector in Europe. <https://doi.org/10.18690/978-961-286-353-1.15>
10. Hartwig, K., and, F. M.-J. of H. C. for the P., & 2020, undefined. (n.d.). From housing instability to a home: The effects of furniture and household goods on well-being. *Muse.Jhu.EduKA* Hartwig, F MohamedJournal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved, 2020•muse.Jhu.Edu. Retrieved April 26, 2024, from <https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/1/article/772765/su mmary>
11. Izawa, E., Yamano, T., Safarov, D., & Billetoft, J. (2021). Technical and vocational education and training in Tajikistan and other countries in Central Asia: key findings and policy options. https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=wyg5EAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT9&ots=vedzx1JWl6&sig=zPYOs67vHD8Cg_mn0tLzbH5rKTM
12. Jiboku, J. O., Jiboku, P. A., & Babasanya, A. O. (2021). Poverty and Unemployment in Nigeria: The case for advancement of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET). *International Journal of Economic Behavior (IJEB)*, 11(1), 57–77. <https://doi.org/10.14276/2285-0430.2878>

13. Journal, U. K.-B. A., & 2024, undefined. (2024). Repositioning Technical Vocational Education and Training (Tvet) for Youth Empowerment and Entrepreneurship: An Agenda for Renewed Hope in Nigeria. *Bwjournal.OrgUA KwamiBW Academic Journal*, 2024•bwjournal.Org, 9(2), 7840–6308.
<https://bwjournal.org/index.php/bsjournal/article/download/1751/1594>
14. Keaney, M., & Supervisor, T. (2019). Introducing Circular Economy to the Furniture Industry. <http://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/172514>
15. Margolles & John. (1993). Full House Swap Shop, Weatherford, Texas. Library of Congress. <https://www.loc.gov/item/2017706584/>
16. Mayer, J. (1961). VANCE PACKARD. The Waste Makers. Pp. x, 340. New York: David McKay Company, 1960. \$4.50. <Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/00027162613340167>, 334(1), 190–191. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000271626133400167>
17. Ngor, Z., Education, D. T., Behavioural, S. and, & 2017, undefined. (2017). Enhancing technical vocational education and training (TVET) as a tool for national development in Nigeria: issues, challenges and strategies. *Stm.E4journal.ComZ Ngor, D TambariJournal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 2017•stm.E4journal.Com, 21(4), 35527. <https://doi.org/10.9734/JESBS/2017/35527>
18. Norwich Uni of Arts. (2021, June 3). Is IKEA killing the planet? | Norwich University of the Arts. Norwich University of the Arts. <https://norwichuni.ac.uk/about-us/blog/is-ikea-killing-the-planet/>
19. Pei, X., Italia, M., & Melazzini, M. (2024). Enhancing Circular Economy Practices in the Furniture Industry through Circular Design Strategies. *Sustainability 2024*, Vol. 16, Page 6544, 16(15), 6544. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU16156544>
20. Remanufacturing in the UK: A snapshot of the UK remanufac... - Google Scholar. (n.d.). Retrieved May 3, 2024, from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Remanufacturing+in+the+UK%3A+A+snapshot+of+the+UK+remanufacturing+industry.+Aylesbury%3A+Centre+for+Remanufacturing+and+Reuse&btnG=
21. SUN SKIPS. (2023, February 22). POPs waste: New rules for throwing away soft seating. SKIP HIRE WASTE MANAGEMENT. <https://sunskips.co.uk/news/pops-waste-upholstered-seating- sofas-skip/>
22. Tes. (2024). Swap shop tens and one's visual display aid | Teaching Resources. Swap Shop Teaching Resources. <https://www.tes.com/teaching-resource/swap-shop-tens-and-ones-visual-display-aid-12533210>
23. ZWIA. (2018). Zero Waste Definition. <https://zwia.org/zero-waste-definition/>
24. ZWIA. (2022, May 19). Zero Waste Hierarchy of Highest and Best Use 8.0 - Zero Waste International Alliance. ZWIA. <https://zwia.org/zwh/>